

Analysing artistic network of the Basilian order in Eighteenth-Century Poland-Lithuania: a digital humanities approach

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The research project, titled "Jesuits of the East? Artistic Network of the Basilian Order in Eighteenth-Century Poland-Lithuania" employs Geographic Information System (GIS) and Social Network Analysis (SNA) to explore the connections within and surrounding the Basilian order, encompassing individuals, events, objects, and locations. SNA and GIS offer novel avenues for collecting, storing, and analysing multidimensional data, unattainable through conventional historical methodologies (Wetherell, 1998; Gregory & Ell, 2007). Religious orders present significant analytical opportunities among historical social organisations due to their distinct internal structure, extensive network connections, and abundant written sources (McShane, 2018). The Uniate (Greek Catholic) Basilian order, as one of the largest monastic communities in Poland-Lithuania, comprised over 150 (their number was changing) monasteries and more than a thousand monks, playing a pivotal role in Western-Eastern cultural exchange (Lorens, 2014). Basilians took care of the most important sanctuaries, provided pastoral and educational care, developed modern printing houses; from within them the Uniate bishops were recruited. Therefore, the changes implemented in Basilian monastic complexes depict well the modernising aspirations and social roles of the most influential Uniate actors.

Figure 1. Map depicting number of actions (related with artistic activities) taking place in Basilian monasteries in 18th-century Poland-Lithuania. Number of actions can be understood as granularity or resolution of collected data. Accordingly, for 28 monasteries there is no information about artistic activity, and for almost 50% we have between 1 and 5 actions. Only for 3 monasteries (i.e. Krechów, Podhorce, Krystynopol) there are more than 100 actions. Differences are due to the nature of historical sources: mostly their availability and scope of content. Source: own elaboration in QGIS based on various archival queries.

Figure 2. Graph depicting all possible connections between 700 human actors, 190 monasteries, and 1900 artistic objects collected in the study. Connections represent actions between these entities. Source: Own elaboration in Nodegoat based on various archival queries.

Figure 3. Map showing the spatial dispersion of "Latin" (West) and "Orthodox" (East) elements in Basilian churches. "Latin" elements are side altars, confessionals and pulpits, while "Orthodox" is iconostasis. All other monasteries are shown in grey. The map signals the high level of "Latinization" of the order. Source: own elaboration in QGIS based on various archival queries.

The central goal of the project is to reconstruct the artistic network of the Basilian order, defined as the interconnections among human actors, events, objects, and places. The research questions focus on three key areas: the artistic activity of the order, the uniformity of its artistic expression, and the role of patronage:

- How did the monastic network operate within the Uniate order, bridging the traditions of Eastern and Western Churches?

- Did Basilian superiors and artists promote a universalized artistic vision, or did regional disparities prevail?
- What was the significance of noble founders and patrons in shaping the artistic landscape?

The project draws on diverse historical sources, including written, iconographic, cartographic, and material evidence (in situ art objects). Written sources encompass acts of visitations, inventories, chronicles, building documentation, and correspondence within the Church and with patrons. Historical and contemporary images, along with depictions on maps, complement the available evidence.

To collect, analyse, and visualise the data and address the research questions, a digital humanities toolset is employed, consisting of Nodegoat, QGIS, and Gephi. Nodegoat is used for data model preparation and collection, while QGIS and Gephi are employed for geographical and social visualisations, respectively. The data model, designed in Nodegoat, includes feature types for human actors, places, concrete objects, and events, ensuring data consistency through controlled vocabularies. The use of "actions" in the model links human actors, places, and objects, aligning with event-based modelling principles (Yuan et al., 2015) and CIDOC-CRM "event" (E5) class (Bekiari et al. 2024, p. 60-61). For instance, an action of building a new church takes place in a certain monastery and involves different people of particular roles (monastery superior, patron, architect, contractors, etc.). "Actions" are differentiated not only by their references to particular classes, but also by the type (e.g. building, planning, painting, etc.). The database contains approx. 1600 actions, 700 human actors, 190 monasteries, and 1900 artistic objects. In the analytical stage, Nodegoat, QGIS, and Gephi are employed for filtering, querying, spatial analysis, and graph metrics. For better understanding, the results are put on the map (fig. 1) or graph (fig. 2).

Figure 4. Map exemplifying regional differences in artistic solutions employed by the order. Towers flanking a façade of the church occur in the northern (Lithuanian) province, while domes mostly in southern (Polish). All other monasteries are shown in grey. Source: own elaboration in QGIS based on various archival queries.

The database enables us to answer initial research questions. Basilians were combining Tridentine Catholicism with the spiritual and material heritage of Eastern monasticism. Tracking specific objects in monasteries illustrates the spatial dispersion of "Latin" and "Orthodox" elements and the synthesis of diverse influences. For instance, Basilians introduced "Western" elements, such as confessionals, pulpits, and side altars, while remodelling the most "Eastern" object - the iconostasis (fig. 3). Regional differences within the order, particularly between Polish and Lithuanian provinces, are evident, impacting formal solutions in artworks (fig. 4). Patron preferences often outweighed the rules or preferences of the monastic community, with many Basilian monasteries relying on the financial and organisational support of Polish-Lithuanian magnates (fig. 5). As a result, some great complexes were erected, while other projects were executed only partly or never realised.

The proposed approach holds broader implications for network analysis in history, art history, and related disciplines (Kovacs, 2016; Lozano, 2021). Notably, it makes use of "event-based modelling" with the inclusive concept of "action," facilitating the correlation of different actors with places and artefacts. This approach, integral to the workflow, can be adapted for similar research endeavours. Additionally, the method suggests a means to integrate diverse sources into a single data model, allowing for analysis in various geographical and social contexts. Future works may include such activities as aligning the model to upper-level ontologies (e.g. CIDOC-CRM).

Figure 5. Graph showing monasteries and their patrons. Blue circles and dots represent monasteries, and red depict founders. The larger the circle, the more patrons the monastery had and, vice versa, the more monasteries were founded by a single patron. Two monasteries are significant (Rzym/Rome and Krasnopuszcza) as they had many patrons, whereas Atanazy Szeptycki, Mikołaj Bazyl Potocki and Stanisław Szczesny Potocki were involved in the highest number of monasteries. Own elaboration in Nodegoat based on various archival queries.

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